

THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS

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Directly to ensure the economic security of the countries, to have an open dialogue with the representatives of entrepreneurship and small business and to support them, to ensure the rapid development of export and import substitute goods production, logistics services special economic zones play a major role in attracting direct foreign investment. At the same time, developing countries, unlike industrialized countries, focus primarily on achieving a high level of industrialization, that is: modernization of industry, attracting foreign capital, improving the skills of workers and introducing new technologies. Special economic zones are important in this regard.

A special economic zone is an area with defined boundaries and a special legal regime, specially allocated for the purpose of attracting foreign investments and local investments, high technologies and management experience for the rapid socio-economic development of the respective area. Special economic zones can be organized as follows:

- free economic zones;
- special scientific and technological zones;
- touristic and recreational zones;
- free trade zones;
- special industrial zones.

According to Andrey Kutepov, Chairman of the Economic Policy Committee of the Council of the Russian Federation, today 68 regions have access to only one preferential regime, which allows the SEZ to attract a wide range of investors. The nature of the implementation of projects by the residents of technological-innovative SEZs implies the creation of new products, developments and technologies aimed at import substitution, as well as at the increase of imports. Based on the specifics of their activity, these resident companies attract qualified and highly paid personnel, increasing the costs of forming a wage fund compared to companies that are residents of other types of special economic zones. In accordance with the provisions of the law, a free or special economic zone is an area intended for national and (or) foreign entrepreneurs, with limited and preferential economic conditions, with a special

legal status compared to the rest of the territory. They are directed towards certain goals [1].

According to Sirazetdinov R.M., Salaxieva L.R., the main goal of state investments in the special economic zone is the development of the innovative economy, industry, and the scientific and investment sector. This is done by:

- attraction of foreign investors (capital);
- ensuring (increasing) the number of jobs;
- creation, development, increase of export products;
- import substitution;
- application of new models of management on the basis of experience, work;
- support of start-up entrepreneurs, small businesses;

It serves as an impetus for the development of a certain region, as well as a certain field of activity [2].

In accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a special economic zone is an area with defined boundaries and a special legal regime, specially allocated in order to attract foreign investments and local investments, high technologies and management experience for the rapid socio-economic development of the respective area [3].

Among the CIS countries, the legislation of the Russian Federation provides a legal definition of "a special economic zone - a part of the territory of the Russian Federation, defined by the government of the Russian Federation, where a special regime applies for the implementation of business activities and where the customs procedures of the free customs zone are applied" [4].

A special economic zone is an area where a special regime of economic activity of foreign investors and enterprises with foreign investments, as well as local enterprises and citizens, is legally established. Free economic zones (hereinafter SEZs) are created for social acceleration, economic development, development of trade-economic, scientific-technical cooperation, all-round exploitation of natural resources of our country, increase of export opportunities, development of high-quality and import-substituting products. aimed at expanding the output. In the following years, large-scale work on the establishment of SEZs was carried out not only in Uzbekistan, but also in other countries of the world. In the last 20 years alone, the number of free economic zones in the world has increased 6 times: in 1998, their number was about 900, and in 2018, their number was 5,400, of which more than 1,000 are the last are formed in five years. About 500 SEZs are expected to open their doors to investors in the coming years. For 147 (197) countries in the world, such zones

have become a convenient tool, a mechanism that can be used to turn the economic situation for the better.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order for the national economy to reach a new state of quality, it is necessary to introduce new criteria and goals in the field of economic policy. It will be necessary not only to strengthen the achieved achievements, but also to implement measures that ensure a new quality of economic growth. One of such aspects, in our opinion, is the analysis of the investment potential of the regions of the country, the results achieved as a result of attracting foreign investments, including the import of modern techniques and technologies from abroad and their assimilation and management experience, creation of new jobs and innovation projects. is mastery. Therefore, the development of the region's economy depends on the extent to which investments and loans are attracted and how efficiently they are used. One of the effective ways to develop the economy of a particular region is to establish a free economic zone in this region. For this reason, they are provided with a number of benefits, as we discussed above. Due to the organization of these regions, it is possible to achieve some effective achievements in the economy of our country.

List of used literature:

1. M. Rafikova, M. Mukhammadiyeva THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN THE UZBEKISTAN ECONOMY // SAI. 2022. No. A7.
2. Sirazetdinov R.M., Salakhieva L.R. Osobie ekonomicheskije zoni kak instrument innovacionnogo razvitiya natsionalnoy ekonomiki: effektivnost, tendentsii, problemi i puti ix reshenia // Rossiyskoe predprinimatelstvo. — 2016. — T. 17. — No. 21. — S. 2827-2836. — doi: 10.18334/rp.17.21.36925
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Special Economic Zones". LRU-604 17.02.2020. <https://lex.uz/docs/4737511>
4. Vokhidova Mehri Khasanovna FREE ECONOMIC ZONE AS A VIEW OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE // ORIENSS. 2021. №4.
5. Ochilov, B., Hoshimov, J., & Butayev, J. (2024). IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHDA MAMLAKAT INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGI: NAZARIYA VA AMALIYOT (Monografiya).
6. Hoshimov J. Actual problems of improving the system of attracting foreign investments to the economy: Xorijiy investitsiyalarni iqtisodiyotga jalb etish tizimini takomillashtirishning dolzarb muammolari //MOLIYA VA BANK ISHI. – 2023. – T. 9. – №. 3. – C. 9-14.

7. Tulaganova R. THE ROLE OF THE STOCK MARKET IN ATTRACTING INVESTORS //Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 7. – С. 49-52.
8. Saloxov S. THE ROLE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN FINANCING “GREEN ECONOMY” PROJECTS //Models and methods in modern science. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 5-9.
9. Холмаматов Ф. К. ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИДА ЛИКВИДЛИЛИК РИСКНИНИ БОШҚАРИШ АМАЛИЁТИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ МОЛИЯВИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИГИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2024. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 375-382.
10. Сулейманов И. БАНК ТИЗИМИ ВА ИҚТИСОДИЁТНИНГ РЕАЛ СЕКТОРИ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯСИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШ АСОСИДА ТИЖОРАТ БАНКЛАРИНИНГ РЕСУРС БАЗАСИНИ МУСТАХКАМЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ: https://doi.org/10.55439/ECED/vol23_iss5/a20 //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 5. – С. 122-129.
11. Murtazaevich K. S. Improving Foreign Investment Insurance in Uzbekistan //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2023. – Т. 20. – С. 68-79.
12. Aminova N. ХОРИЙИ ИНВЕСТИСИЯЛАРНИ ЈАЛБ ҚИЛИШ ОРҚАЛИ О 'ЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ТАШҚИ ІҚТІСОДИЙ FAOLIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //Ўзбекистон республикаси суғурта бозори учун кадрлар тайёрлашнинг ҳозирга ҳолати, муаммолари ва ривожланиш истиқболлари. – С. 132.
13. Sugahara, S., & Ochilov, B. (2023). The Experience of The Japanese State in Increasing Investment Activity in Uzbekistan.
14. Tursunkulovich, S. R. (2023). SOME THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCES REGULATION OF MONEY SUPPLY. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 16, 60-71.
15. Tursunkulovich, S. R. (2023). SOME THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCES REGULATION OF MONEY SUPPLY. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 16, 60-71.
16. Шомуродов Р. Т. Опыт зарубежных стран в осуществлении монетарной политики //Молодой ученый. – 2021. – №. 23. – С. 443-449.